

UNIVERSITY OF ZIMBABWE

FACULTY OF ENGINEERING AND THE BUILT ENVIRONMENT DEPARTMENT OF MINING CHEMICAL AND METALLURGICAL ENGINEERING

TITLE:

**DEVELOPMENT OF A DIGITAL HAZARD MONITORING SYSTEM AND RISK
BASED ASSET MANAGEMENT FRAMEWORK: A CASE OF BATTERY
POWERED TRACKLESS MOBILE MACHINERY (BTMM) IN MINING
APPLICATIONS.**

*A research project submitted in partial fulfilment for the requirements for the award
of a Bachelor of Science Honors Degree in Mining Engineering*

By

Nzira Kudzaishe

R199090V

Supervisor: Eng V.T Kurira

DECLARATION

I, Kudzaishe Nzira, do hereby declare that the work presented in this report is my original research work except of citations of previous work by other authors which has been referenced. No part of this research work has been previously published for the quest of any degree in this or any other university or institution.

I, therefore, declare that this project was presented according to the rules and regulations that govern the award of the Bachelor of Sciences degree of the University of Zimbabwe.

Signature of author.....

Date.....29-05-23.....

CERTIFICATE OF APPROVAL

The University of Zimbabwe has approved this project by Kudzaishe Nzira as partially fulfilling the requirements for the award of the Degree of Bachelor of Sciences.

Name	<u>Signature</u>	<u>Date</u>
Supervisor:
Examiner (1):
Examiner (2):

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DEDICATION

To my beloved Raymond, Martina, Anesuishe and Matipaishe Nzira. This work is dedicated to you all, with heartfelt gratitude for everything you have done for me.

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ABBREVIATIONS

AC	Alternating Current
Ah	Ampere-hour
AM	Asset Management
API	Application Programmer Interface
BTMM	Battery Powered Trackless Mobile Machinery
CMS	Cable Monitoring System
DC	Direct Current
FHF	Fire Hazardous Faults
FMEA	Failure Mode and Effect Analysis
HMS	Hazard Monitoring System
Kw	Kilowatts
LHD	Load Haul Dump
Li-Ion	Lithium Ion
NPC	Net Present Cost
OEM	Original Equipment Manufacturer
RIAM	Risk Informed Asset Management
RPN	Risk Priority Number
WSN	Wireless Sensor Network

ABSTRACT

The project underlines the growing potential of renewable energy to enhance sustainability in highly mechanised mining operations. It brings the risk-informed asset management (RIAM) concept into perspective, highlighting the practical approaches that can be implemented in managing the inherent risks that come with new technologies. The emphasis was to reduce fire incidences in operating lithium battery-powered trackless mobile machinery (BTMM).

The research proposes the hypothesis that a guarantee on the return on investment in BTMMs is dependent on the risk tolerance of the asset management system in place. A thorough investigation of the BTMM system enabled the identification of the critical components whose failure modes were likely to pose fire hazards. To which analysis of the causal factors revealed the need to monitor anomalous hazards in the vehicle's operation since the failure of the protection systems would increase the probability of the hazards propagating to a fire. It was established from the study that the significant risk influencers were dysfunctional processes and systems. This necessitated the development of a digital hazard monitoring system which can be used to conduct real time variance analysis of key parameters in processes, and the storage of data from the parameters being monitored. The identification of variances and the interpretation of the machine data would then aid making risk informed decision regarding the areas where the asset management systems needs to be optimized. A framework was then designed to be used as a tool for formulating strategies to enhance the risk tolerance of asset management systems.

The strategies within the proposed risk management framework can be implemented by any mine seeking to adopt battery-powered trackless mobile machinery. It can also be used as a benchmarking tool for companies currently using the electric machines that intend to improve the dependability of their asset management systems.

CHAPTER I: INTRODUCTION

1.1 Battery-powered trackless mobile (BTMM) machinery in the Mining Industry.

As the mining industry shifts its focus to more sustainable mining practices, there has been a growing interest in using battery-powered trackless mobile machinery. Battery power is the future of mining (Sandvik, 2020), and renewable energy now stands as a sustainable power supply for mining machinery.

Jacobs (2014) conducted a cost-benefit analysis of tethered electric vehicles. It was concluded that the significant economic benefit from electric machinery came from ventilation savings. The study was based on a Net Present Cost (NPC) analysis illustrated in Figure 1.1. Ventilation savings outweighed the additional cost of powering the electric units due to the ventilation system's power, which was four times larger than the power of the loaders. The power is directly proportional to the cube of the airflow. Electric machines require 20% less airflow, and this translates to a massive reduction in power consumption.

Figure 1.1: Life cycle cost comparison of diesel and BTMMs. (Source: Jacobs, 2014)

According to African Mining, several mining companies in South Africa have started to adopt electric mining equipment. Locally, the Zimbabwe Platinum Mines published in their annual general report of 2021 that they were to begin a feasibility study on BTMMs which they later reported to be finalised in 2022. Electric options have been developed for various machinery in the mining cycle: haul dump vehicles, haul trucks,

drill rigs, bolters, dozers, front-end loaders, graders, emulsion loaders, shotcrete sprayers and utility vehicles.

1.2 Limiting factors that are slowing the adoption of BTMMs.

Although battery-powered trackless mobile machinery (BTMMs) present a promising sustainable solution, some risks and challenges are associated with their adoption.

- Higher capital outlay than diesel counterparts,
- Accessibility of cost-effective charging solutions in remote mining locations.
- Low reliability of grid power supply.
- Uncertainty of technology advancements

The charging infrastructure for BTMMs is still being developed, and mining operations may need the necessary infrastructure to support large numbers of electric vehicles. Depending on grade and peak power variances from load requirements during the work cycle, they have a limited range per charge. This can result in downtime while vehicles are charged, reducing productivity. The limitations can be further categorised as factors solved by resource allocation and financial capacity or those necessitating sound engineering, design, and innovation. The high initial purchase and infrastructural development costs are insignificant, given that there is enough funding for the project. However, the hazards posed by BTMM contribute towards a negative scepticism of the technology, considering the industry's high regard for maximum productivity and safety. The machine is susceptible to several faults and malfunctions that present significant hazards throughout its life cycle. The level of control over such uncertainties is highly dependent on the capabilities of the risk management systems that address the critical issues within the asset management portfolio. (Komljenovic, 2008). The approach currently used for diesel units regards total machine shutdown as the most critical risk of failures. In this case, the major consequence of its unavailability is reduced productivity. Nevertheless, BTMMs pose a more serious concern as the high voltage system adds a relatively new set of consequences that are more catastrophic and costly.

Lithium-ion batteries that power BTMMs are in the range of 700-800V, and such high voltages are a critical safety hazard. In addition, their work cycles are characterised by frequent acceleration and deceleration in rough terrain with varying grades. Such operating conditions render the BTMM vulnerable to external thermal and mechanical impacts that result in catastrophic errors within the machine. Furthermore, BTMMs tend to be quieter than conventional vehicles, making them harder to detect and increasing the risk of collisions (Halim,2021).

Figure 1.2: The 'bathtub' failure rate curve (Source: Wikipedia)

Mining companies can be reluctant to adopt BTMMs due to the uncertainty of the failures and risks since it is still in its early stages. The bathtub describes the high probability of failures in the early stages of deploying new technology. During its operations, measures are then put in place to mitigate these challenges, and the number of failures is reduced; however, towards the late maturity stage of the machine, failures emerge due to machine ageing and wear and tear. Therefore, the maintenance system adopted plays a pivotal role in reducing failure rates during the operation of BTMM. In addition, the risk management systems adopted should account for the functional and operational safety of the asset.

1.3 Battery Electric Vehicle Fires

Fire accidents are a significant safety concern for battery-powered vehicles, which has hindered electric vehicles' progressive development. Studies by Ji (2022) have shown

that lithium battery is causal to these fires. Different chemistries of lithium batteries were studied, and it was discovered that the higher the energy density of a specific chemistry, the higher the instability of the cell module leading to higher fault probability. The most dangerous consequence of such faults is a process referred to as thermal runaway. Figure 1.3 illustrates how thermal runaway propagates. Wikipedia defines the term "thermal runaway" as a process that speeds up as the temperature rises, generating energy in the process that raises the temperature even more. It happens in scenarios where the increase in temperature alters the chemical reactions such that there is a further increase in temperature, often leading to a destructive result, a fire.

Figure 1.3: The stages of thermal runaway in a lithium battery (Source: Li, 2020)

1.4 Incidents of electric vehicle fires in mines.

80% of the world's BTMMs are deployed in Canada; thus, very few case studies are available. In addition, mines are very confidential with their data; thus, obtaining information on such incidences is typically difficult. However, there is an exception to Glen Core Mine. The mine is Canada's largest underground mine and North America's second largest. It has employed BTMMs in its operations since 2017, and they have had a BTMM fire incident in its operations.

1.4.1 Incident 1: Sudbury/Onaping District

On July 6, 2020, two workers who were troubleshooting an electric boom truck were the first to report the fire outbreak. The workers stated they were stranded behind the burning vehicle without access to compressed air. After the first contact, there was no further communication between the two contractors within a few minutes. Following the implementation of emergency protocols, the rescue team went underground and came across the fire incident site at 01:55 hours. The location was characterised by

intense heat and thick, dark smoke. The team continued to cool the unit for two hours after announcing the termination of the fire at 04:36hrs.

Figure 1.4: The electric truck burning in the underground mine.(Source: Ontario Mine Rescue, 2020)

Figure 1.5: A heat map of the burning vehicle (Source: Ontario Mine Rescue, 2020)

1.4.2 Incident 2: Southern District

Sept 19, 2019, at approximately 17:30, an underground worker noticed smoke and fire from a charging/parking station. The worker noted that one vehicle was on fire and proceeded to a safe place. Emergency procedures were then immediately implemented. Then at 19:40hrs, the rescue team descended to attend to the matter. They used a water truck to extinguish the fire after 3 hours. The team ensured that the gasses in the mine were clear and the area was barricaded. Unfortunately, the fire consumed three vehicles and all the service infrastructure in the charging area.

Figure 1.6: Remains of burnt BTMMs. (Source: Ontario Mine Rescue, 2020)

1.5 Project Statement

To develop a risk based asset management framework and hazard monitoring system for electric vehicles in mining applications.

1.6 Justification

Traditional and manual inspections have their limitation on data capturing frequency and accuracy. With the application of high-voltage mobile machinery in the mining industry, these approaches to asset planning and decision-making in the machine life cycle phase expose the operations to the risks that come with innovations. The in-built protection devices and safety systems are not guaranteed 100% protection against the lithium battery fire risk. Thus, it would be the duty of the mine to assess their risk preparedness and response assessment. Dysfunctional risk management systems would then increase the probability of a fire incident.

The fire incident results in substantial losses to the mine. For example, consider a platinum mine that has a section producing 20 000 tonnes of ore per day at a head grade of 3.5g/t utilising battery-powered machinery comprising of a drill rig, bolter, LHD and 2 haul trucks There is a single charging station and suppose a fire incident occurs

involving the whole fleet during charging. The following are the losses that a mine can incur in that fire incident, assuming that a contractor will provide relief equipment within two days of the incident. The current price of platinum is US\$ 1076 per ounce, approximately \$35 per gramme.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{The lost value} &= \text{price per ounce} \times \text{grade} \times \text{tonnage per day} \times \text{days to replace equipment} \\ &= 35 \times 3.5 \times 20000 \times 2 \\ &= \text{\$US 4 900 000} \end{aligned}$$

Table 1.1 Lost value in a BTMM fire incident.

Cost	US \$
Machine <i>(Each at US\$800'000)</i>	4'000'000
Repairing infrastructural damage. <i>(Charging, ventilation and accessories)</i>	200'000
Rescue, investigation and compensation and restoration <i>(water, resources. injured, deceased)</i>	5000
Lost value	4 900 000
TOTAL	9'105'000

Such a worst-case scenario translates to a potential loss of **\$US 9 105 000**. However, such a catastrophic incident can be averted by establishing a resilient risk management culture before fully adopting the vehicle. Thus, by analysing electric mining equipment as a complex adaptive system, the project will present the tool and approach that can be integrated to manage the BTMM fire risk effectively. In the context of this research, the management of the fire risk will be regarding providing a basis for minimising the likelihood of the risk.

1.7 Aim

To reduce mobile machinery fire incidences related to lithium batteries and their high voltage systems in mining operations.

1.8 Objectives

1. To investigate the main BTMM electrical components and identify the faults that pose a fire hazard.
2. To identify the root causes of the risks associated with using BTMM.
3. To develop a hazard monitoring system.
4. To design a risk-based asset management framework for the BTMM.

1.9 Summary

The project is a research and design exercise. It underpins an integrated approach to the effective and efficient utilisation of BTMMs in mining applications through systemic identification and management of the technology's inherent fire risk.

CHAPTER II: LITERATURE REVIEW

2.0 Introduction

A thematic approach was used to carry out the literature review. Lithium technology is still in its early development stages; thus, there is little information on the fire characteristics of mining vehicle batteries. This chapter presents the theoretical background of the research work on the fire behaviour of the lithium battery. It also discusses the principles of asset management and the global trends in digital asset management in the mining industry.

2.1 Battery Electric Vehicle Work Cycle

An operation cycle for a mining battery electric vehicle (BTMM) in a mining environment typically involves the following steps:

Figure 2.1: Typical cycle of the main unit operations of BTMM.

The BTMM is charged before it is put into operation. Charging times may vary depending on the size and capacity of the vehicle's battery, as well as the charging infrastructure available. Before the BTMM can be used, it must be pre-checked to ensure its systems function correctly. This involves checking the battery charge level, the brake system, the steering system, the lights, and other safety features. The BTMM is then used to transport personnel, equipment, or materials throughout the mine or the respective shift work, including loading and dumping ore and bolting for support,

development, and production drilling. Once the BTMM has completed its operation cycle, it must be charged again before it can be used for the next cycle. On average, the best-performing BTMMs are reported to require two batteries in an 8-hour shift.

Equipment companies have developed mobile charging solutions for on-site charging for electric mining equipment. However, stakeholders in the industry are sceptical about the impact of battery charging and changes on their overall productivity. To address this issue, equipment manufacturers continuously improve their products by engaging with their clients and meeting their needs. As of November 2022, two recent battery swapping technologies are available for load-haul-dump (LHD) machines, but effective planning and scheduling are still necessary to ensure maximum throughput from the machines.

Table 2.1 Overview specifications of two selected electric LHDs.

LHD	Motor Size		Capacity (Tons)	Battery (Ah)	Battery Charge Minutes	Swap Time Minutes
	Chassis (Kw)	Hydraulics (Kw)				
Sandvik Machines Lh518b	540	200	18	576	60	<5
Epiroc Machines Scooptram ST14	200	160	14	375	150	<10

2.1.1 Sandvik Battery Changing System.

Earlier versions of Sandvik LHDs used LTO lithium-titanium oxygen and fast-charge batteries without battery replacement. In the current versions, it applies Artisan Lithium ion phosphate batteries. The battery charging technology developed by Sandvik is currently the fastest compared to other OEMs. The battery replacement process in Figure 2.2 is also renowned since it is an automatic process that does not require extra infrastructure for their 18-ton LH518B loader that takes at most 5 minutes.

Figure 2.2: Sandvik patented battery replacement system(Source: Sandvik, 2022).

2.1.2 Epiroc Battery Changing System

Epiroc is a subsidiary of Atlas Cop-co. Their most recent machine, the Scooptram ST14 loader has a load capacity of 14 tonnes; Epiroc reports that the batteries used in the LHD loader can be charged from zero to 90% in 50 minutes. Lithium-ion phosphate batteries are also used to power the LHDs. The machines can be recharged with an external charger, and the battery replacement infrastructure is shown in Figure 2.3 .

Figure 2.3: Epiroc battery replacement system infrastructure.(Source: Epiroc ,2022)

2.2 BTMM related faults that have a fire hazard

2.2.1 Arc Flash (Short Circuit)

A short circuit occurs when unlike energy charges come into direct contact, resulting in an arc flash. Arc faults are classified as series or parallel and can be difficult to detect through over-current monitoring. Repeated contacts between the cable and chassis during bumpy driving can initiate intermittent and periodic short-circuit parallel arcs.

Both series and parallel can cause damaged components to ignite and result in a vehicle fire. Liu et al. (2021) empirically describe an arc's development in four stages on a 350V system.

Figure 2.4: The development of an arc fault(Source: Liu, 2021).

1. The first phase is the short circuit phase. After that, there is a rapid increase in current.
2. The second phase is the arc growth phase. It is when the arc starts to grow between the hollow gap due to a high short current. The arc power remains steady with little fluctuations.
3. The third phase is arc stabilisation, where the arc transforms into a long-column steady state. Power and resistance remain stable during this phase.
4. The fourth phase is arc-breaking, where the fuse is triggered and switches off the circuit. All the arc characteristics dramatically return to their initial state since the circuit restores to an open status, and the resistance becomes infinite.

Typically, electric arcs can attain extremely high temperatures, ranging from a few thousand to tens of thousands of degrees Celsius. The heat dissipated by an electric arc can harm the adjacent materials and may lead to a fire. Apart from the arcs within the battery, the arcs can originate from the internal wiring of the components or the bus cables linking the components during operation or maintenance work.

2.2.2 Overcurrent

When charged or discharged at a rate exceeding its rated capacity, an overcurrent fault poses a fire hazard in the lithium battery. A higher discharge rate results in a higher temperature increase as well. The entropy change in a lithium cell can contribute more than 50% of the total heat generated at the standard 1C discharge rate (Jeon, 2021), which is a rate that totally discharges a battery in an hour. The rating of most BTMM batteries is in the range of 250Ah. This means a 1C collates to 250A being discharged in one hour. A rate of 0.5C, where the battery is discharged at half the standard rate, will maintain a constant temperature and an insignificant gradual increase with time. A rate of 5C would imply the discharge of the same battery in 12 minutes. As shown in Figure 2.5, the temperature gradient increases with the discharge rate. Batteries have an average operating temperature (0-40°C) beyond which the battery's internal reactions might be compromised, leading to an increased probability of thermal runaway.

Figure 2.5: The thermal effect of different charging rates. (Source: Jeon, 2021)

2.2.3 Overcharging

Thermal runaway occurs during overcharging because of heat accumulation (Liu et al., 2022). When a lithium-ion battery is overcharged, the increase in temperature causes the battery becomes unstable, and the electrolyte inside the battery can break down, forming gas bubbles and releasing heat. As the battery continues to overcharge, the temperature inside the battery can increase rapidly, causing a chain reaction that generates even more heat. The heat generated by side reactions contributes more to the

total heat generation. The power supplied to a battery is directly proportional to the heat generated within the battery. Figure 4 depicts the temperature response of a small cell to a power supply. A 4.5W power input at the 15000s mark had a subsequent temperature increase of 3°C. This is a result of the increase in the internal energy of the battery cell. This relationship is also true for high voltage configurations, and the temperature variances are also marginalised. Maintaining a lower charge rate close to the rated current allows for the operation and charging of the battery at lower temperatures which are safer. The discharge at the same rated power of 4.5W at the 30000 mark had a resultant increase in temperature by 5°C.

Figure 2.6: Thermal response to overcharging.(Source: Liu,2022)

2.2.4 High temperature

The batteries are rated to operate between 0-40oC. When the temperature of a lithium-ion battery rises above a certain threshold, it can cause the electrolyte inside the battery to decompose, releasing flammable gases and heat. As the battery continues to heat up, it creates a positive feedback loop that generates even more heat and gas. This can cause the battery to reach the critical temperature, known as the thermal runaway temperature, at which point it can no longer be controlled or stopped (Kim et al., 2023).

Figure 2.7: A heat-temperature thermal runaway model (Source: Kim et al., 2023).

2.2.5 Protection error

The BTMM has inbuilt sensors, breakers, fuses, shunts, switches, relays and actuators that perform control and protective functions in the case of electrical surges or out-of-range situations. The protection errors can be a protection device failure or design flaws that omit necessary surge protection devices in complex high-risk circuitry. Mechanical or electrical failure of cooling system components such as pumps, radiators, fans, or temperature sensors can also lead to cooling system failures and increase the probability of thermal runaway. In the case of an electrical surge, an inactive current sensor will fail the inbuilt management systems to react accordingly, thus increasing the likelihood of a fire. Switches are manual circuit breakers usually tripped before maintenance work. A defective switch poses a significant hazard for the workers, which can also result in personnel electrocution. Fuses are supposed to automatically cut off the current supply in the case of a surge. The Glencore fire incident discussed in Chapter 1 resulted from the absence of a fuse in the 3-battery service disconnect points. Figure 2.8 shows the service disconnects before and after the incident. The image on the far right shows the shunt along the circuit. If the circuit design was done with the utmost consideration for the vehicle's protection, a fuse should have been put in place of the shunt.

Figure 2.8: Unfused shunts before and after a fire incident. (Source: Ontario Mine Rescue, 2020)

2.3 BTMM Maintenance

Roeth (2021) describes the technology to be in its early maturity stages. Thus the objective of maintenance in this regard would be to maximise its availability. The High Voltage (HV) system requires specialist training. To ensure proper safety measures high, voltage safety gear such as face shields and rubber gloves should be available. However, early adopters are less likely to have their staff; instead, they will rely on the OEMs to provide expert technicians, and as the production and adoption of BTMMs increase, there will be a demand for expert technicians. For the software and electrical system, the maintenance of BTMMs by technicians requires a laptop computer or service tool equipment. Frequent software updates will be a routine aspect of the maintenance process. In order to install and maintain heavier components like motors and batteries, equipment like cranes and chain blocks may be necessary.

Figure 2.9: Interaction of components in the electric vehicle. (Source: Grunditz,2017)

Grunditz (2017) studied the interaction of the components in which troubleshooting errors and faults during maintenance was based on examining the related systems. Several faults in diesel engines are related to their wiring system, and this issue is more pronounced in electric vehicles due to their increased amount of wiring. In addition, the connectors are more prone to experiencing issues with improper installation and inadequate insulation. Han (2020) researched the maintenance of electric vehicle wiring, and it was concluded that instead of repairing it, placing an order for replacement cables would be necessary. In an earlier study by Khrennikov (2019), the monitoring of the machine and charging station was proposed for the HV electrical systems. Sensors are the tools that address this need. However, the sensors can also read false signals or not sending at all. The sensors report to the management system, which regulates the deviations by cutting the current supply in the case of an overcurrent scenario or initiating cooling mechanisms when the temperature rises.

Figure 2.10: The distribution of sensors in the electric vehicle (Source: IHS Markit, 2018).

The major limitation is that these sensors do not have a data logging system appended to them. The actuating systems also react to pre-set thresholds, but the parameters would have been deviating for an extended period without being noticed. Such a mode of blind operation increases the risk of fires if the sensor or actuating device fails. There is limited research on minimising the likelihood of HV-related fires in mining applications. The vast majority of literature was focused on mitigating the impact. Other researchers are emphasising developing more stable lithium chemistries less likely to undergo thermal runaway. Thus, it is necessary to equip mining asset management systems better to better cope with the technology in the current era.

2.4 Asset Management

The British Standard, PAS 55, defines asset management as the set of systematic practices and actions allowing an organisation to manage its assets and asset systems along with their associated performance, risks and expenditures over their life cycles to achieve its organisational strategic plan (PASS 55). A more elaborate definition given in the ISO 55000 defines asset management as the coordinated activity of an organisation to realise value from its assets (ISO 55000). Asset management is usually applied to physical assets but can also be applied to financial, technical, human, information, and intellectual assets. For mining equipment, asset management systems are implemented to efficiently manage and optimise risk levels in the use of assets. The

effectiveness of risk management systems employed in a mining ecosystem depends on the asset management systems approach quality.

Figure 2.11 Organizational tiers within asset management systems (Source: PAS 55)

The highlighted levels in the figure illustrate the hierarchy of an asset management system within an organisation. It starts below the pyramid with the management of the individual assets in which the management of risks through specific planning and scheduling of maintenance and work execution for each unit. It also illustrates the requirements of each stage with regard to the planning of the asset. For example, individual assets have short-term plans where maintenance planning is carried out. The top levels are definitive of a holistic approach which entails all the integrated systems around the operation of the assets in clusters. This involves the establishment of synergies that ensure the sustainable utilisation of the asset.

2.4.1 Challenges in asset management

Strategic planning and asset management are crucial for mining organisations, and to plan, there is a need to forecast factors affecting operational decisions. However, accurate forecasting of these factors is challenging due to uncertainties which make it difficult to predict specific events. Greyling (2017) highlighted the need to accept the uncertainty and instead focus on establishing a systemic approach to uncertainty management. Figure 2.10 shows a risk matrix for the management of uncertainty in projects devised by Smith (2006). Causal explanations were given regarding why

traditional project planning and risk management were insufficient in dealing with unforeseen factors in novel projects. Finally, specific management tools are presented as solutions for guiding such high-uncertainty projects.

Figure 2.12 Managing uncertainty in projects (Source: Smith, 2006)

The efficacy of asset management strategies was studied by Huber et al. (2013). The researchers discovered that, even with the adoption of various asset management techniques, the organisation encountered challenges in the reliability and maintenance of its equipment. The following were the factors which needed further improvement ;

- lack of standardisation,
- poor quality of data,
- ineffective inter-departmental communication

Brown (2013) also examined the challenges that asset managers were currently facing and the possible challenges to be faced in the future. A severe challenge discussed was the resistance to change. The study was similar to Huber's in the discussion on inadequate interdepartmental integration and poor communication between departments. In 2015 best practices were proposed by Venkataseshan to some of these challenges. The solution emphasised the effective and efficient management of physical mining assets, and it encompassed monitoring equipment performance, scheduling maintenance activities, tracking equipment usage, and optimising asset utilisation.

Finally, a study was carried out by Schuddebeurs et al. (2016) to investigate the application of data mining as a tool in asset management in the mining industry. The authors' findings highlight the potential of data mining techniques in detecting recurring trends, anticipating equipment malfunctions, and curbing equipment downtime. The investigation sheds light on employing data analytics to enhance asset management procedures within the mining industry.

2.5 Risk Management in Mines.

Risk management involves the process of recognising, assessing, and ranking potential risks. It is then followed by the efficient allocation of resources in order to reduce, oversee, and manage the likelihood or consequences of the risks. There are two types of engineering uncertainty: aleatory and epistemic uncertainty. Aleatory uncertainty refers to random events. Equipment failure is an example of aleatory uncertainty, which is expressed as a probability or frequency. This failure is predictable but at an unpredictable time, caused by degradation mechanisms in the equipment. A risk assessment measures uncertainties in harmful events.

Epistemic uncertainty is related to limitations in knowledge. Epistemic uncertainty makes decision-making risky and complex. Some recommend sensitivity studies instead of uncertainty propagations. Therefore, it is crucial to account for all uncertainties for successful decision-making in mining. Mining organisations risk inefficiency or survival threat without action.

Figure 2.13: The Swiss cheese model (Source: Wikipedia)

The primary objective in the process of risk identification is to establish a level of assurance that every significant risk is identified. Upon acknowledging the presence of potential hazards, it is necessary to examine possible causes and scenarios. In the context of risk assessment, scheduling the identification of potential hazards is an essential exercise that should be carried out diligently to prevent incidents from occurring as a result of areas of weakness, as defined by the Swiss cheese model in Figure 2.11. Several methodologies exist for the purpose of risk identification. A selection of these is discussed below.

2.5.1 Failure Mode and Effect Analysis (FMEA) -

A systematic review of the failures of a machine and their subsequent effect. It is mainly done for evaluating machinery during its design phase. Its purpose is to :

- To identify potential failures and their effects
- To quantify the severity
- To determine the potential causes of failures according to severity rating
- To facilitate the design of controls that will prevent the failure from occurring
- To formulate corrective actions
- Improve the ease of detecting such failures early
- To recommend design improvement actions

2.5.2 Action Error Analysis

It is an approach used to investigate conceivable human mistakes such as communication breakdown, errors of choice and omission and errors of arrangement. It is a brainstorming exercise which requires individuals who understand the area of concern.

2.5.3 Root Cause Analysis

There are various ways to conduct a root cause analysis the following two methods were used in this research.

5 Whys and Hows

This is a process in which a potential problem is retraced back to its root cause. The procedure is a systematic approach to investigating root causes. Sakichi Toyoda, the technique's creator, believed that repeating the question "why ?" and "how ?" five times lead to a clear understanding of the problem and its possible solution. Using the five whys involves a deep understanding of the problem, while implementing the “five hows” aids in formulating the solution.

The fish-bone diagram

It presents a problem-solving method that aims to identify potential root causes and evaluate plausible solutions. This type of diagram is referred to as an Ishikawa after its developer, Kaoru Ishikawa, and is also known as a herringbone diagram or cause-and-effect diagram. Fish-bone diagrams are frequently employed in analysing the underlying causes of problems in quality control or the adoption of new products. They are also utilised for generating ideas and organising.

Figure 2.14 The Fish-bone diagram (Source: Enlaps)

2.4.4 Machinery Hazard Identification (MHI)

The procedure involves considering the potential for a range of unwanted scenarios against a checklist of possible causes in machinery. The analysis is broken down into subsystems.

2.5.5 Workplace Risk Assessment and Control (WRAC)

Potential incidences in the workplaces are identified and the likelihood and consequence of each potential event is used in a quantitative risk matrix. It involves the identification of hazards followed by an analysis of the risk nature of the hazards. Finally action is then taken to minimize the risk.

2.6 Digital risk management systems developed

The global industry has shifted from a resource-based work approach to a more information-dependent arena in recent years. Data science has proved helpful in this transition (Galar et al., 2016). It involves the collection of data from connected devices or systems within an organisation's operating sphere for the purpose of control and analysis. For example, such systems can be of use in establishing solid asset management systems. The innovative insights and leverage realised can then be used in decision-support risk management and automation.

2.6.1 The Internet of Things (IoT)

According to Massaro (2022), the beginning of any modern system is the integration of sensors. To assess the condition of assets, data has to be collected on the performance conditions and the operational and environmental factors influencing the assets, as failures may occur due to the abnormal operational or environmental conditions of all these stages. The sensors, however, should be reliable and economical so as not to adversely affect the benefits of monitoring the assets. Aziz et al. (2020) illustrated the potential applications of IoT in mining maintenance systems. His paper greatly supports academics and developers who are working to create an interactive environment for the many potential Internet of Things applications. The Internet of Things (IoT) and data mining tools supported by the cloud that has sensors and actuators can significantly change a passive management system into an intelligent and active system. The relative advantages are the reduction in time spent investigating or diagnosing a fault, reduced loss resulting from prompt response to a risk event and less human interaction leading to reduced error in operational systems.

2.6.2 Real-Time Monitoring

Big data is an enabling tool in monitoring systems. It is where several sensors collect data and enable control over the process allowing for improved maintenance or machine-to-machine communication.

Brodny (2022) developed a sensor network for monitoring equipment in order to reduce downtime. The sensor data can be used by technicians to identify patterns and trends that may be used to predict failure. This would allow them to take corrective action before the equipment breaks down. These can make use of the previous work by Sikora in 2012, in which they aimed at improving prediction models that were applied in systems monitoring hazards and machinery.

Real-time monitoring has since been applied in the industry in various applications. Li and Liu (2009) discuss the design of a sensor network that is self-aware and able to quickly detect variations in structures caused by underground collapses in an underground coal mine. The paper was centred on Wireless Sensor Networks (WSN) and the manner in which it is linked to the Cable Monitoring System. It inscribes routing protocols, collision prevention, data aggregation, and linking to the CMS system. There has been another proposal by Sun et al. (2012) for an IoT-based real-time monitoring and cloud computing system for a tailings dam to detect the water level and the dam stability.

2.7 Prototype Development

In the design of engineering systems prototypes are used to illustrate real life systems. They use miniature components referred to as modules. Components are available in various sizes and versions depending on the intended use. In addition to general accessories such as jumper wires, breadboards resistors and LEDs the following components were selected for this project

The development board

The research made use of the Node MCU ESP8266, which is a logic circuit that is re-programmable and has the capability of connecting to a Wi-Fi network. The processing unit has frequency range of 80MHz to 160MHz. It has an accessible RAM of 96KB

and ROM of 512KB to 4MB. Before being used, it requires libraries to be installed in the integrated development environment.

Sensors

The sensor modules used in this project were the:-

- SW18010p Vibration and Impact Sensor,
- ACS712 Current sensor,
- LM35d Temperature sensor.

The sensors accept a power input of 3.3V which is provided by the board, although they can accept even up to 5V. The current and vibration sensors communicate with the Arduino programme through the digital pins and the temperature sensor through the analogue pin. The OneWire library and Dallas Temperature libraries are required in order for the Arduino programme to read from the sensors.

Online server Communication

The image shows a screenshot of the ThingSpeak login page on the left and a diagram of the data flow on the right. The login page includes the MathWorks logo, a navigation bar with 'Channels', 'Apps', and 'Support', and a 'Commercial Use' link. The main content area contains a sign-in form with a 'Sign In' button and a 'Forgot Password?' link. The diagram illustrates the data flow: 'SMART CONNECTED DEVICES' send data to 'DATA AGGREGATION AND ANALYTICS' (ThingSpeak), which then feeds into 'MATLAB' for 'ALGORITHM DEVELOPMENT' and 'SENSOR ANALYTICS'.

Figure 2.15 The Thingspeak login page.

The Node MCU ESP8266 is capable of connecting to the Wi-Fi and this enables it to communicate with online servers. The server used in this project was the Thingspeak service from Mathworks. It requires a personalised account to use its functions. It also has data analysis tools which can be used for other projects.

2.8 Summary

The literature review enabled the identification of the faults which were fire hazardous and how they developed. It also provided a theoretical basis for asset and risk management development with regard to digital technologies.

CHAPTER III: METHODOLOGY

3.0 Introduction

An analytical research and design approach was employed to achieve the aim of this research project. First, a desktop study was conducted to have a solid appreciation of the battery-powered technology. Then, a thematic literature review was also conducted to provide the theoretical background of the research work. The research plan in Figure 3.1 was formulated and executed accordingly.

Figure 3.1: The research plan

3.1 Desktop Study

A desktop study was conducted to gather technical data on BTMM functionality. This involved sourcing materials from the internet, academic literature from the University Library, and technical reports from the professional community.

3.1.1 Electrical Failure modes with a fire hazard.

- Potential electrical failure modes that could lead to a fire in a battery-powered vehicle were identified.
- It was achieved by reviewing scholarly papers, past incidents, industry standards and text in the electrical engineering field that discussed electrical faults and their consequences.

3.1.2 BTMM main components and their faults, errors and failure modes.

- The critical electrical components of the BTMM were identified from manufacturers' specifications along with their functions.
- A list of the components was compiled and categorised as those in the: -
 1. Propulsion system
 2. Energy system
- The likelihood of a hazardous fire fault was investigated for each electrical component.
- Faults and possible causes were studied from articles, text, and scholarly papers discussing Cause and Effect Analysis and Failure Modes and Effect Analysis and were reviewed.

3.1.3 Physical asset management systems.

- Operation and maintenance procedures and systems of electric mobile mining machinery were studied.
- The study aimed to identify the critical inputs and processes required to utilise mine physical assets efficiently.
- Technical reports, ISO standards, industry guidelines and operator manuals were analysed to gain a comprehensive understanding of the various stages and requirements involved in operating and maintaining electric mobile machinery.

3.2 Analysis and Brainstorming

3.2.1 Machine Failures

- A qualitative machinery hazard identification was used to analyse the faults that were fire hazardous
- FMEA of related electric components was also analysed from secondary sources.

3.2.2 Root Causes

- A Root Cause Analysis was conducted to identify possible root causes of the previously discussed failure modes.
- A list of root causes was compiled and classified according to the following categories:
 1. Processes & Systems
 2. Human
 3. Machines
 4. Environment
- These were analysed concerning the operation of BTMM across the stages of its life cycle.
- This was achieved through a qualitative analysis that aimed to identify the latent causes of the failure modes by a systematic approach to how a process could go wrong and providing logical explanations of how the factors could result in an increased likelihood of the risk.
- Incident reports were also used to identify root causes of errors and faults in mining machinery..

3.2.3 Framework Design

- A matrix was designed based on the afore mentioned root causes
- The analysis of the root causes of faults was utilised in brainstorming a systematic approach to manage the asset effectively.
- This stage involved the construction of a framework that generates asset management objectives.
- This stage aimed to identify gaps where the current asset management approaches fell short of the desired state and propose feed-forward controls to address the gaps.

3.3 Prototype Programming

- An IoT system was developed to provide a basis for remote monitoring of the BTMM.

3.3.2 Software programming

- The logic board was programmed to control the components using Arduino software
- A program using the C programming language.
- A Thingspeak Online server by MathWorks was used for the remote monitoring.

3.3.3 Testing

- Analogous simulations of hazards were then used to test the system's response.
- A soldering heater gun was used to test the response of the temperature sensor momentarily.
- A 1.5A current source was connected to a 3V lithium cell, and the setup was used to simulate a BTMM charging scenario; this setup was used to test the current sensor.
- The vibration sensor was shaken by hand.

3.4 Limitations

- The major limitation encountered was the lack of field data on the battery electric vehicle; secondary sources of information had to be used instead. Credible sources and peer reviewed papers were used in this research work to ensure validity of the data.

CHAPTER IV: RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.0 Introduction

This chapter entails the findings and outcomes of the research work. It presents the hazardous errors, faults and their respective root causes. The proposed concept of the monitoring system and the risk framework are also discussed in this chapter.

4.1 Faults within BTMM Components.

A fire in the electric vehicle can result from these faults occurring in the battery or elsewhere in the vehicle and then propagating to the battery. The lithium battery is likely to undergo thermal runaway when subjected to mechanical, thermal, or electrical abuse. They are designed to operate in harsh conditions such as high temperatures, frequent vibrations and underground water, requiring further protective design considerations. The onset of these forms of abuse results in faults within the vehicle. For this research, the study emphasised managing the fire risk by making use of the previously discussed FHF:

- Arcing or Short circuits
- Overcurrent
- Overcharging
- Over Temperature
- Protection error

The study identified 26 electric vehicle drive train components, and their failure modes were qualitatively analysed. The distribution of the fire-hazardous faults is given in Figure 4.1. The analysis compared the likely occurrences of the FHF in the propulsion system and the power system, and a more detailed matrix is given in Appendix A.

Figure 4.1: The distribution of the fire-hazardous faults and errors in the drive train components.

The count of hazards in the energy system was approximately twice that of those in the propulsion system. The distribution of the FHF in the drive train shows a higher occurrence in the energy system. This is owing to the fact that it hosts the power supply, power storage and primary supply management system; thus, its functional operations encompass the risks of High Voltage Direct Current systems. The propulsion system is more prone to fatigue failures due to the mechanical rotation of the components it holds. The cables that link these components might be the sources of hazards within the propulsion system. It is also to note that the vehicle has more protection sensors, relays and switches, which could pose a fire hazard if inoperable. The vehicle is safeguarded from the onset of faults by these subsystems. Arc flashes, Overcurrent, Overcharging and High temperature are faults that can be caused by man, machine and environment. And they resemble some form of abuse. Due to the dynamic behaviour of these faults, the following section will rather discuss the faults and errors of the protection components in both systems.

4.1.1 The propulsion system

This system is responsible for providing traction and propulsion of the vehicle. Appendix A-1 provides the distribution of the faults in the components. The components are excluded from being affected by overcharging since there is no relation between the

two systems. However over-heating ,arcs and short circuits might still occur in the wiring of the components in the propulsion system. The qualitative analysis below will look at the faults of the components that should provide protection.

Brake Pedal Sensor

A potential fault could be a failure to accurately measure the response from the brake pedal, which could lead to a failure to stop the vehicle and cause a collision that could damage the battery cells.

Motor Temperature Sensor

Failure to accurately read and report temperature readings to the BMS could result in failure to actuate the cooling system. This would increase the probability of a fire in the motor.

DSP Relay

A failure to correctly process the right signals for operation, such as forward, reverse, or neutral, could lead to loss of control of the vehicle, which could increase the likelihood of a collision.

4.1.2 The energy system

The occurrence of faults in the power system was discovered to pose a significant fire hazard. This could be attributed to the functional nature of the components in the sense that their operations evolve around the high-voltage battery. There is a significant portion of components that fall susceptible to the FHF's. This could be attributed to the high voltage DC charge and storage system that operates in close proximity with the rest of the components. A breakdown of the faults is presented in Appendix A-2. An analysis of the protection errors is given below.

Battery Management System

If the systems fails to distribute charge evenly in the battery cells. A damaged cell might undergo thermal run away and ignite the battery.

Li-Ion Battery Relay

The relay might get stuck on the off position and fail to cut supply of DC electricity to the rest of the vehicle. This increases the likelihood of arcing and short circuits

Li-Ion Battery Current Sensor

The current sensor could fail to read temperature readings from the cells, and in case of an out-of-range situation, the battery management system will not take corrective action. This could lead to overcharging or over-discharging, which could cause a fire.

Li-Ion Battery Temperature Sensor

If the temperature fails to read and report a high temperature in the Li-Ion battery, this could lead to a thermal runaway.

Li-Ion Battery Service Plug

An accidental electrical arc or short circuit could cause damage to the battery or the electrical system if the service plug fails to disconnect the battery from the BTMM's electrical system during maintenance or repair.

Charge Port Temperature Sensor:

An operating error or fault could lead to damage to the charging infrastructure or the BEV due to overheating or a failure to prevent damage due to extreme temperature fluctuations.

Fail-Safe Circuit Breaker:

Suppose it fails to cut the current flow in case of a surge in the electric circuitry. The system components might get damaged, and a thermal runaway event might occur if the fault reaches the battery.

Charging Relay:

A potential fault could be a failure to cut the flow of electrical power from the charging infrastructure to the BTMM's battery. This might result in the battery being overcharged.

4.2 Root Cause Analysis of the Faults

Considering the changes and advances in mining technology, there is a need to road map why and how faults might occur in using BTMMs. Thus, this section will present the probable root causes of faults, errors and failures of the vehicle power train. The mining environment consists of man, machine and the processes and systems that

govern their interactions. These spheres form the sources of error and faults this project will emphasise. Appendix B 1 enlists the potential root causes, which were drafted from desktop research and analysis of the previously mentioned faults using the "5 Why Analysis". The main causal factors are shown in Figure 4.2.

Figure 4.2: A fish-bone diagram of the causal factors.

Figure 4.3 Demography of the causal factors

4.2.1 Processes and Systems

This is the largest class amounting to 43% of the root causes identified in this research. Processes and systems refer to the loopholes in cycles, procedures, policies, and strategies that govern the unit processes involving the asset.

In light of battery-powered trackless mining machinery, the current statutory instruments within the Zimbabwean regulatory framework do not have a section that;

1. Guides the transition from diesel to battery power
2. Governs the processes of BTMM in mining applications.

This means that mines planning to adopt BTMM should either establish an efficient risk management system through a dedicated internal responsibility system or engage their equipment manufacturer to consult on functional safety aspects of operating the machine. A lack of management competency in streamlining the transition exposes mining companies to nonstandard practices that might be risky for the personnel and machinery. (Hemmanth, 2022). The fire risk culminates from the failure to identify specific hazards during the unit operations of the BTMM. A case study example is the Glencore incident, where a BTMM vehicle was towed incorrectly, damaging the inverter, which led to a fire. The underlying root cause was the absence of a standard towing procedure.

The failure of a mine to accurately delineate its Work Breakdown Structure (WBS) along with a complementing Risk Breakdown Structure (RBS) would lead to poor and insufficient hazard and risk management assessments. This would increase the probability of unaddressed erroneous events occurring blindly, thus increasing the likelihood of a fire-hazardous fault. Apart from the policies and risk assessments, the mine should also be able to assign the most appropriate technologies to manage the assets (Massaro, 2022). A poor asset management system will be characterised by the following:

- Inadequate traffic management systems

- Lack of data collection, storage, processing and transfer capabilities
- Delays in the communication of risk events

4.2.2 Human

Most errors that occur due to human-machine interaction emanate from a lack of knowledge, as supposed by Nongera (2022). If a mine is to adopt BTMMs, it is necessary to assess the competency of their operators and maintenance teams and provide adequate training programmes to better equip the personnel, even for a well-trained workforce. People have a subjective element in how they operate individually and as a team (Smith,2006). This leads to errors made through complacency and negligence. Some of the errors made by employees as a result of this phenomenon are:

- Distracted driving or fatigue
- Skipping or neglecting pre-checks and maintenance.
- Divided attention when attending to a BTMM during maintenance or pre-checks.
- Willfully operating defective equipment.
- Not reporting near misses.

Thus, a strong risk culture must be established to promote a more unified industrial psychology paradigm that employees can cultivate. Human behavior is difficult to control, and deviation from risk management policies, standards and regulations can be costly for the mine if not resolved. For example, the shift crew responsible for charging a vehicle can make errors such as using an incorrect charger or overcharging the battery. These actions cause damage to the battery pack and cause short circuits and arcs, which might increase the likelihood of thermal runaway. In addition, the management can fail to prescribe the minimum charge level for charging or battery replacements. A low threshold can result in dendrite formation in the battery, potentially resulting in an internal short circuit that might cause a thermal runaway. Table 4.1 shows the actions that can be done by personnel and the consequence of their actions.

Table 4.1 Action and Effect Analysis of personnel on BTMM.

Personnel	Action	Effect
Operator	Hard acceleration	Early failure from fatigue and stress
	Sudden braking	
	Over speeding	Collisions
	Distracted driving	
	Tampering with safety devices	Machine vulnerability to hazardous fire faults
Maintenance	Neglecting pre-checks and maintenance.	Increased likelihood of unidentified errors propagating into catastrophic failure.
	Using wrong tools	Increased likelihood of arcing or short circuits (uninsulated service tools).
		Inaccurate diagnoses
	Deviating from standard procedures	Increased likelihood of errors that result in thermal runaway or a BTMM fire.
	Lack of risk management culture	Maintenance will be taken as a routine task, and proper attention will not be given to eliminating sources of risks in the machine.
Management	Failure to establish and enforce risk management	Uncontrolled hazards

systems in human-machine interactions	Increased likelihood of the risk from deviations from procedures by low-level employees.
Wrong decisions and the failure to make the right decisions in BTMM operations.	BTMM susceptibility to blind risks

4.2.3 Machine and Tools

Machines and Tools account for 18% of the root causes of the risks in this research. These are the faults that occur due to internal errors due to manufacturing defects, wear and tear and ageing and the reliability of the respective tools used in the maintenance and pre-checks of the machine.

Manufacturer defects in the design of BTMM wiring and electrical components can cause electrical arcing or short circuits. Inadequate protection against electrical faults or insufficient cooling systems can also cause overheating. Inadequate insulation or insufficient protection against physical damage can cause safety risks such as fires or other malfunctions. The effects of wear and tear in the BTMM are primarily identified within the battery. The battery has the following sub-components; the active material, current collectors separator, organic solvent terminals and casing (Jeon, 2011) .

Table 4.2 Internal failure modes of the Li-ion battery (Hendricks, 2015)

Component	Potential Failure modes	Potential Failure Mechanism	Cause	Effect
Active material	Lithium plating and	Chemical reaction	Wearout from Charging the battery at	It can cause a short circuit

	dendrite growth on electrode surface		low temperatures or high rates	if dendrites puncture separator
Organic solvent	Gas generation and bloating of cell casing.	Chemical decomposition of solvent	Overstress from High external temperature, overcharging of the cell	Increased diffusion resistance, and may lead to thermal runaway
Separator	Separator breakdown	Mechanical damage	Dendrite formation, external crushing of cell, drastic voltage reduction	High heat generation due to joule heating, bloating of cell casing,
Terminals	External corrosive path between positive and negative leads	Chemical corrosion reaction	Accidental shorting of the terminals	High heat generation
Casing	Internal short circuit between anode and cathode	Mechanical stress	External load on cell or mechanical damage	High heat generation

From the above faults The likelihood, severity and ease of detection can be quantified and multiplied to get a Risk Prioritization Number (RPN) . The failure modes are the classified into risk levels based on the RPN. For the faults mentioned earlier, the following risk classifications were made by Hendricks (2015).

Figure 4.4: Risk prioritisation key for the lithium battery.

The component failures inherent to manufacturer defects ageing, wear, and tear within the battery have a low likelihood of occurrence. This is attributed to the effort made by OEMs to deliver quality products with minimal manufacturer defects. They also ensure a proper material selection of the components they employ in manufacturing their batteries. Though less, the likelihood of occurrence is a non-zero function, and it is impossible to tell which component will fail, when it will fail and under what conditions it will fail. Considering the high severity of an eventual failure and the low detectability of the failures, the overall risk priority is increased. The ease of detection is low for the internal components, casing, terminals, and vehicle wiring, which can be inspected in operational pre-checks; the failures can be identified by visual inspection.

4.2.4 Environment

The mine environment is the least contributor in the sources of risks identified. However, it is characterised by harsh ambient conditions that pose several hazards to the BTMM (Hemmanth. 2022). The complex electrical nature of the machine is a new system in the underground mine. This necessitates a re-assessment of the hazards within the mine environment. The environmental conditions in which it operates must be

investigated to assess the source of failures. If, in the case of an underground mine, a machine operates in a zone where a rock fall occurs, the battery unit can get damaged and possibly lead to a thermal runaway. Underground mining environments are prone to dust and debris, which can accumulate on the surfaces of the BTMM components and cause overheating or short circuits. Dust and debris can also clog the air intakes and filters, reducing the efficiency of the cooling and ventilation system(Han, 2022) . High humidity and exposure to water can cause corrosion of the metal parts of the BTMMs, such as the battery terminals and electrical connectors.

The charging bay where batteries are charged should not be located near aquifers. Any water in contact with the charging apparatus and batteries could cause short circuits. High temperatures can cause thermal runaway in the battery pack, resulting in a fire or explosion. Underground mining equipment traffic volumes might not match the size of excavations when the scheduling is ineffectively carried out (Venkataseshan , 2015) . Underground mines have limited space for vehicles to manoeuvre, which can increase the risk of collisions and damage to thC Qe BTMM components.

4.3 The hazard monitoring system (HMS)

Figure: 4.5: The hazard monitoring system prototype.

With regard to the reliability of the BTMM, there is a need to identify the onsets of the faults emanating from the various causal factors previously discussed. A model was developed to conceptualise the hazard monitoring system. The system will enable the

early identification of hazardous operating conditions. Figure 4.6 shows the circuit diagram for the components.

Figure 4.6: The circuit diagram of the sensing and alarming system.

4.3.1 The Thingspeak cloud server

Figure 4.7: The application programmer interface key provided in Thingspeak.

In order to enable online monitoring of the sensors, it was pertinent to establish an online server that could provide cloud service. A MathworksThingspeak account was created in which a monitoring channel was opened. Next, the communication protocol

was initiated by copying the Channel ID and API key shown in Figure 4.7 and pasting them into the Arduino code, as illustrated in Figure 4.8 The ESP8266 would then communicate via the Wi-Fi network after connecting successfully.

4.3.2 Arduino code for remote monitoring


```
NZIRA_KUDZAI SHE IoT Project | Arduino 1.8.19
File Edit Sketch Tools Help

NZIRA_KUDZAI SHE IoT Project_$
// Including Libraries
#include <DallasTemperature.h>
#include <WiFi.h>
#include <WiFiClient.h>
#include <WiFiServer.h>
#include <WiFiUdp.h>
#include <OneWire.h>
#include <ThingSpeak.h>
#include <ESP8266WiFi.h>
#include <ESP8266HTTPClient.h>

// Wi-Fi and Thingspeak credentials

Const char* ssid = "SLS Engineering";
Const char* password = "123456789";
Const unsigned long channelID = 2086426;
Const char* apiKey = "5R76NEJQLXFDXMM46";

Const int ledPin = 2;
```

Figure 4.8 Libraries used for sensor and Thingspeak communication with the ESP8266


```
NZIRA_KUDZAI SHE IoT Project_$
while (WiFi.status() != WL_CONNECTED) { // Wait for Wi-Fi connection
  delay(1000);
}

pinMode(Buzzer, OUTPUT); //Buzzer
pinMode(ledPin, OUTPUT); //LED

}

void loop() {

//READ TEMPERATURE SENSOR
temp = sensors.requestTemperatures();
temp = sensors.getTempCByIndex(0)

//READ CURRENT SENSOR
float SensorRead = digitalRead(A0)*(5.0 / 1023.0);
float curr = (SensorRead-2.5)/multiplier;

//READ SHOCK SENSOR
vibr = digitalRead(5);
```

Figure 4.9: Reading data from the sensors

After installing the necessary libraries for the sensors and initialising variables. The sensors were assigned to their respective pins. In the setup function, communication between the ESP8266 and the online server was established. In the loop function, the readings from temperature, vibration, and current sensors are stored in their respective variables as shown in Figure 4.9. The loop function included the code in Figure 4.9 to send the data to the Thingspeak channels.

```
//Sending to Thingspeak
WiFiClient client;
HTTPClient http;
String url = "http://" + String(SERVER) + "/update";
String data = "api_key=" + String(apiKey) + "&field1=" + String(temp) + "&field2=" + String(curr) + "&field3=" + String(v);
http.begin(client, url);
http.addHeader("Content-Type", "application/x-www-form-urlencoded");
int httpCode = http.POST(data);
http.end(); // End the HTTP request
```

Figure 4.10: Sending data to the Thingspeak channels.

4.3.3 Code for the alarming system.

The design included a buzzer and a sensor to resemble an alarm system. This was because, in a real-life scenario, it is impractical to constantly look at the monitoring screen in wait for anomalies. Threshold limits can rather be set to alarm responsible individuals of an unwanted hazard. To which responsible authorities can then log in to their monitoring domains and make corrective action.

A screenshot of an IDE window showing C++ code for an alarm system. The window title is 'NZIRA_KUDZAIHE_loT_Project_\$. The code is as follows:

```
if(curr>currLimit){
digitalWrite(ledPin, HIGH);
tone(Buzzer, 1000);
delay(5000);
noTone(Buzzer);
digitalWrite(ledPin, LOW);

if(temp>tempLimit){
digitalWrite(ledPin, HIGH);
tone(Buzzer, 1000);
delay(5000);
noTone(Buzzer);
digitalWrite(ledPin, LOW);

if(vibr>vibrLimit){
digitalWrite(ledPin, HIGH);
tone(Buzzer, 1000);
delay(5000);
noTone(Buzzer);
```

Figure 4.10: Code for the buzzer and LED.

4.3.4 Testing

Real-Time Monitoring

After connecting the model to the Thing-speak online server, the model was tested by simulating different operating scenarios to represent possible hazards. First, a soldering heater gun was blown on the sensor, and a temperature rise was seen on the monitoring screen. After that, the vibration sensor was shaken by hand. While testing the vibration sensor, the heater gun accidentally pointed towards the temperature sensor, and the temperature began to rise. For the current source, the 1.5A source was replaced by a 5A source and the changes in current were noted in the monitor. From the arbitrary threshold limits set in the programme for testing purposes, the alarm system the buzzer rang and the LED went on successfully when each limit being was reached.

Figure 4.11: The feed from the channels.

Data capture and analysis

Thingspeak allows the storage and exportation of data, and Figure 4 shows the graph from the temperature sensor data highlighted in red, similar to the one in the Thingspeak monitoring interface. In addition, integrating Excel enables quantitative data analysis, which can be useful in diagnosis and prediction.

Figure 4.12: Data integration in Excel

4.3.5 Proposed Application

The system will have four subsystems, the sensor system, logic unit monitoring, and alarm system. The system can be used in both WSN and CMS designs. It also allows the integration of other relevant sensors into the architecture. Figure 4.13 shows the strategy employed to identify hazards in the vehicle at the rectangles shaded in yellow. The illustration is based on the onset of environmental causal factors. The same can also be carried out for the other causal factors previously discussed. Various sensors can be placed in various locations in the BTMM based on predetermined hazard prone components or zones. The temperature sensors will detect the high temperature scenarios. The vibration sensors will allow the notification of shocks due to rockfalls impact or collision. The current sensors will also allow the identification of short circuits and over current scenarios. The system will aid in the investigation of faults and hazards as to their sources and possible occurrence sequence referencing to

Figure 4.13: The strategic positioning of the sensors to identify hazards

4.4 The asset management framework

Risk informed asset management is a fundamental design element. The likelihood and impact of an event must be quantified in order to design a mine-specific system that reduces the likelihood of risks (Komljenovic 2008). In the context of this research, the likelihood of an event is the likelihood of an FHF occurring in the machine. The risk management system can also be defined as an internal responsibility system. It governs the policies, strategies and approaches in risk control. The framework that this project presents allows a mining company that seeks to adopt BTMMs to set risk based management objectives.

The proposed asset management framework provides an integrated physical asset risk management approach that can be used during the utilisation BTMMs in order to assess the risk tolerance of their asset management system. Figure 4.14 shows the complete framework, which can be used to formulate and set strategic objectives specific to the asset management portfolio.

4.4.1 The change management phase

This stage is when the asset is still in its early adoption phase where the mine is still configuring their resources and systems to align their operations with their objectives. The stage involves the installation of charging stations and replacing existing diesel units with electric units and a test on the aptitude of workers towards the technology. The BTMM, as an asset still in its developmental stages, presents a new

set of risks stemming from the previously discussed root causes. Before Zimbabwean mines adopt BTMMs, explicitly defining the resilience of their asset management system by probabilistic methods should quantitatively determine the likelihood and consequence of uncertain events. The risk factors differ from mine to mine, and so do the risk weightings. Additionally, it often requires changes to the organisation's policies and procedures, such as developing new safety protocols and implementing new procedures for maintenance and operation. Therefore, management should ensure minimal resistance to change by facilitating the development of sustainability awareness and risk culture. Objectives are then drafted in this regard.

4.4.2 The capacity utilisation phase

This is the stage where the machine can no longer be regarded as new technology in the context of the maturity that an adopter would have achieved through a successful change management exercise. Passive defects that are not detected during the early stages of the machine can lead to total failure and potential fire hazards. Real-time variance analysis can help identify currents, voltage, and temperature anomalies and compare them against optimal levels. Algorithms can be used to filter out and identify these anomalies, preventing potential safety risks and improving the overall safety of the BTMM. Objectives can be set to integrate digital technologies that can improve the effective management of the hazards. The early identification management and possible elimination of these faults can possibly reducing downtime and improving maintainability, safety, and sustained productivity.

4.4.3 The perpetual development phase

Perpetual development refers to the ongoing process of improving the design and performance of asset management systems to minimise risk levels. Whilst OEMs are currently undertaking this phase advancing their products and services, mining companies should likewise have a research and design agenda in their management portfolio. Mines should be able to adapt to the inevitable changes that will erupt as a consequence of technological advancement or regulation by setting relevant objectives for their future (Smith, 2006). This process inscribes the practical approaches to successfully establishing organisational harmony with the new technology. It can also

make use of other new technologies to aid the effective management of the change process.

Figure 4.14 The Asset Management Framework.

4.4.4 The needs assessment matrix (NAM).

The proposed process of setting objectives makes use of a relation-matrix to visualise the objectives according to the issues they address. The matrix in Table 4.3 shows the assessment matrix. It is based on the previously discussed causal factors and can be used to identify areas of weakness and strengths in an asset management system. It begins by defining the four spheres

- Machine (M) : BTMM types acquired,
- Human (H): Operators, Electricians, Technicians and Management
- Processes(P): Policies, Procedures, Schedules
- Environment(E): Excavation Dimensions, Geotechnical issues, Ambient Conditions

Table 4.3 The asset management needs assessment matrix.

	Machine	Human	Processes	Environment
Machine	M	Human Machine Interaction	Machine Processes and Systems Design	Machine Environment Interaction
Human	Human Machine Interaction	H	Human Process and System Design	Human Environment Interaction
Processes	Machine Processes and systems Design	Human Processes and System Design	P	Environmental Interference with Processes and Systems
Environment	Human Machine Interaction	Human Environment Interaction	Environmental interference with Processes- and Systems	E

The HMS designed in this project can also be used to identify areas of need in the utilisation of the machine. Strategic objectives are designed to be set according to the mutual dependence of factors in the spheres. There are six unique relations in the matrix.

1. The Human Machine Interaction (HMI) :

It encompasses the objectives that will be set to minimize the risks that might happen as a result of human action on the machine. This involves action by operators, service personell.

2. *The Human Environment Interaction (HEI)*

These are the objectives that will be set to minimise risk that are a result of environmental factors on human performance and actions. This includes ergonomics and level of familiarity with workplaces.

3. *The Machine-Environment Interaction (MEI)*

The assessment of environmental factors that adversely affect the operation of BTMMs is used to create objectives. These include controlling rockfalls, temperatures moisture and dust hazards.

4. *The Machine-Process and Systems Design (MPSD)*

The objectives set in process and system design would account for bottlenecks and loopholes in the utilization of the asset. These include traffic management systems and optimized work, charging , and maintenance process design.

5. *The Human Processes and Systems Design (HPSD)*

These are the objectives that will be set to minimise human related breaches of standard processes and. It also includes considering management decisions on the systems and policies that govern human execution of tasks.

6. *The Environmental Interference with Processes And Systems (EIPS)*

These are the objectives that are set to establish equilibrium between the environmental adverse conditions and the overall process design. This might include adoption of monitoring systems, changes to the location of stations or excavation redesigning.

How it works

Figure 4.15 : A flow chart of how the frame work and matrix are used.

4.5 Chapter Summary

The chapter presented the asset management framework that aims to reduce the likelihood of risks occurring in the utilization of the BTMM. It involves setting objectives to control risk levels by systematically eliminating or managing the root causes of the fire hazardous faults.

CHAPTER 5: CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATION

5.1 Conclusion

The research aimed to reduce the likelihood of a fire in high-voltage battery-powered trackless mobile machinery operations. In addition, it provided an approach that could control the risks during the transition from diesel to electric machinery in mining. The following conclusions were made on each objective.

1. To investigate the fire hazard faults of the BTMM components.

The fire hazardous faults (FHF) were found to be arcing or short circuits, overcharging, high temperature. The failure of protection systems gives precedence to the propagation of the FHF. This research concluded that the most hazards were from the energy storage and supply system.

2. To investigate the root causes of the risks of utilising BTMM.

It was also concluded that the occurrence of fire resulted from a series of hazards that were not identified across a wide source spectrum. The sources were analysed in four subgroups; Machine, processes, human and environment. The leading root cause was the process design and the systems and policies governing the processes.

3. To develop a digital hazard monitoring system.

The remote monitoring of the hazardous faults enables early action response. In addition, the visual representation enables informed decision-making, and the data collection capabilities enable the integration of prediction tools.

4. To construct an integrated asset management framework for the BTMM.

The effective and efficient management of new technologies can be improved by setting risk based objectives towards the management of physical assets. The framework forms a practical approach that can be used to equip asset management systems.

5.2 Recommendation

The Fourth Industrial Revolution is gaining momentum within the industry and there is more to be discovered technologically. Thus, intensifying asset and risk management within the scope of mining engineering education curricula in this regard would aid in the maximum capacity utilisation of technologies in a more efficient way. Mines should embrace the fourth industrial revolution mind-set and establish Wireless Sensor Network (WSN) infrastructure and support services for the monitoring of assets. The essence of remote monitoring also depends on the asset management strategies adopted and can be marginalised if the response actions are delayed or ineffective. The sensors used in this research were for testing purposes. In practice more robust and sensors can be used. Mines should also adopt OEM monitoring solutions that they provide. In addition more research should be done in these areas:-

1. Formulating statistical risk tolerance indices to measure the elasticity of an asset management system which can be used to further refine the Needs assessment matrix.
2. Research and development of stable lithium chemistries are less likely to undergo thermal runaway.
3. The development of overcurrent protection systems and robust sensors applicable to the complex architecture of BTMMs in harsh mining environments.

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7.0 APPENDICES

Appendix A1: Fire risk matrix for the propulsion system.

Component	Over current	Over-charging	Arc Flash / Short circuit	Over Temperature	Protection Error
Electronic Controller	X	-	X	-	-
Digital Signal Processor					
Traction Motor Inverter	X	-	X	-	-
Permanent Magnet Synchronous Traction Motor	X	-	X	X	-
Transmission System	-	-	-	-	-
Motor Position Sensor	-	-	-	-	-
Motor Speed Sensor	-	-	-	-	-
Motor Temperature Sensor	-	-	-	-	X
Accelerator Pedal Sensor	-	-	-	-	-
Brake Pedal Sensor	-	-	-	-	X
DSP Relay	-	-	-	-	X
Inverter Phases Sensor	-	-	-	-	X
DC/DC Converter	-	-	X	-	-

Appendix A2: Energy storage and supply system risk matrix.

Component	Over current	Over-charging	Short circuit	Over Temperature	Protection error
Battery Management System	X	X	X	-	X
Li-Ion Battery Pack	X	X	X	X	-
Battery On-Board Charging Unit	X	X	X	-	X
Charge Port		X	X		-
Li-Ion Battery Heater Unit	-		-	-	-

Auxiliary 12 V Battery	X	X	X	X	-
Li-Ion Battery Current Sensor	-	-		-	X
Temperature Sensor Of 12V Battery	-	-	-	-	X
Li-Ion Battery Temperature Sensor	-	-	-	-	X
Li-Ion Battery Service Plug	-	-	-	-	X
Charge Port Temperature Sensor	-	-	-	-	X
Fail-Safe Circuit Breaker	-	-	-	-	X
Li-Ion Battery Relay	-	-	-	-	X
Charging Relay	-	X	-	-	X

Appendix B: Component Failure Data

Appendix B-1: Brake Pedal Sensor:

FUNCTIONS	FAILURE MODES	IMMEDIATE CAUSE	MAINTENANCE TASK
Convert brake pedal position in signals to the DSP unit, and control motor speed.	Abnormal reading of values and the incorrect output.	Incorrect Installation	Keeping a checklist of the standard installation procedure
		Connector or terminal failure	Check connector conditions and keep clean from moisture and chemical

B-2: DSP Relay:

FUNCTIONS	FAILURE MODES	IMMEDIATE CAUSE	MAINTENANCE TASK
Process digital signals between inverter and cabin commands.	Abnormal reading of values and output.	Incorrect installation	Having a checklist of the standard installation procedure

Connector/terminal failure
 Check connector conditions and keep clean from moisture and chemical.

Appendix B-3-Inverter Phases Sensor:

FUNCTIONS	FAILURE MODES	IMMEDIATE CAUSE	MAINTENANCE TASK
Detect the 3-phases current supplied to the traction motor by inverter and report to DSP.	Abnormal reading of values and output.	Incorrect installation	Having a checklist of the standard installation procedure
		Connector/terminal failure	Check connector conditions and keep clean from moisture and chemical.

Appendix B-4: Li-Ion Battery Current Sensor:

FUNCTIONS	FAILURE MODES	IMMEDIATE CAUSE	MAINTENANCE TASK
Detect the state of charge and charge/discharge current of the battery pack and report to BMS.	Abnormal reading of values and the incorrect output.	Incorrect Installation	Keeping a checklist of the standard installation procedure
		Connector or terminal failure	Check connector conditions and keep clean from

			moisture and chemical.
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Appendix B-5: Li-Ion Battery Temperature Sensor:

FUNCTIONS	FAILURE MODES	IMMEDIATE CAUSE	MAINTENANCE TASK
Detect the temperature of the battery pack and report it to BMS.	Abnormal reading of values and the incorrect output.	Incorrect Installation	Keeping a checklist of the standard installation procedure
		Connector or terminal failure	Check connector conditions and keep clean from moisture and chemical.

Appendix B-6: Li-Ion Battery Service Plug:

FUNCTIONS	FAILURE MODES	IMMEDIATE CAUSE	MAINTENANCE TASK
Turn off/on the high voltage current for EV maintenance tasks	Stuck in on or off position	Operation or testing error.	Checklist of standard operation and test procedure
		Ageing and deterioration	Inspect relays for physical damage and deterioration.
		Persistent overloading	Replace components if contacts are badly worn or burned, and check the control device

for freedom of operation.

Appendix B-7: Charge Port Temperature Sensor:

FUNCTIONS	FAILURE MODES	IMMEDIATE CAUSE	MAINTENANCE TASK
Detect the operating temperature of the charge port.	Abnormal reading of values and the incorrect output.	Incorrect Installation	Keeping a checklist of the standard installation procedure
		Connector or terminal failure	Check connector conditions and keep clean from moisture and chemical.

Appendix B-8: Fail-Safe Circuit Breaker:

FUNCTIONS	FAILURE MODES	IMMEDIATE CAUSE	MAINTENANCE TASK
Turn off the main power in case of a dangerous malfunction	Stuck in on or off position	Operation or testing error.	Checklist of standard operation and test procedure
		Ageing and deterioration	Inspect relays for physical damage and deterioration.
		Persistent overloading	Replace components if contacts are badly worn or burned, and check the control device

for freedom of operation.

Appendix B-9: Li-Ion Battery Relay:

FUNCTIONS	FAILURE MODES	IMMEDIATE CAUSE	MAINTENANCE TASK
Turn on or off the high voltage current of the battery.	Stuck in on or off position	Operation or testing error.	Checklist of standard operation and test procedure
		Ageing and deterioration	Inspect relays for physical damage and deterioration.
		Persistent overloading	Replace components if contacts are badly worn or burned, and check the control device for freedom of operation.

Appendix B-10: Charging Relay:

FUNCTIONS	FAILURE MODES	IMMEDIATE CAUSE	MAINTENANCE TASK
Turn on or off the charging power to the battery.	Stuck in on or off position	Operation or testing error.	Checklist of standard operation and test procedure
		Ageing and deterioration	Inspect relays for physical damage and deterioration.

Persistent overloading
 Replace components if contacts are badly worn or burned, and check the control device for freedom of operation.

Appendix B-12: Qualitative FMEA analysis of the lithium battery.

Component	Potential modes	Failure	Likelihood of occurrence	Severity of occurrence	Ease Of detection
Active material	Lithium plating and dendrite growth on electrode surface		LOW	HIGH	LOW
Organic solvent	Gas generation and bloating of cell casing.		LOW	HIGH	LOW
Separator	Separator breakdown		LOW	HIGH	MODERATE
Terminals	External corrosive path between positive and negative leads		LOW	HIGH	MODERATE

Casing	Internal short circuit between anode and cathode	LOW	HIGH	MODERATE
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Appendix D

Appendix D-1: Causes of faults errors concerning BTMMs.

HUMAN	MACHINE & TOOLS	PROCESSES & SYSTEMS	ENVIRONMENT
Acceptance to operate poorly maintained equipment.	Software bugs	No regulations governing the operation of electric vehicles in mining.	Insufficient line of sight
Tampering with safety devices.	Design errors	No internal system.	Responsibility Rock falls
Traffic rules violation.	Fatigue	Inefficient planning and scheduling of unit processes.	Poor visibility
Not reporting hazards	Cyclic stress	Processes not in line with formal risk management processes.	Water
Not reporting near misses.	Lack of noise	Lack of risk management system.	Dust
Not following traffic procedures.	Faulty tools	Risk assessment omitted some risks.	Poor road conditions
Not accustomed to new technology.		Lack of traffic management policies	
Using the wrong tools for the job.		Lack of human-machine control policies.	
No appetite for change.		Inability to measure adherence to traffic management policies	

Distracted driving.	Lack of preventive maintenance program.
Deviating from maintenance manuals.	Lack of information from suppliers.
Ignorance	Internal communication breakdown
Operator complacency	Lack of institutional knowledge
	Absence of traffic signage
	Lack of organised maintenance protocol.
	Lack of risk-based planning
	Lack of training initiatives.
	Lack of competency measuring systems
	Lack of hazard detection tools
	Lack of maintenance equipment
	Manufacturer lack of innovation
